

Bioaccessibility and antioxidant activity of *Calendula officinalis* supercritical extract as affected by *in vitro* co-digestion with olive oil

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ABSTRACT

1 Supercritical extracts of marigold (ME) were produced and characterized. The bioaccessibility of
2 terpenes, especially that of pentacyclic triterpenes (PT), the particle-size distribution and
3 antioxidant activity after the *in vitro* co-digestion of ME with olive oil (OO), were determined. ME
4 produced without co-solvent was richer in taraxasterol, lupeol, α -amyrin and β -amyrin than extracts
5 with co-solvent. All terpenes showed high bioaccessibility without OO (>75%). Significant
6 correlations were found between the molecular properties of compounds (logP and number of
7 rotatable bonds) and their bioaccessibility. Co-digestion with OO enhanced the bioaccessibility
8 (around 100% for PT), which could be related to a higher abundance of low-size particles of the
9 digestion medium. The antioxidant activity of the digested ME increased around 50%, regardless of
10 OO. PT-rich extracts from marigold display high bioaccessibility and improved antioxidant activity
11 after *in vitro* digestion, although complete bioaccessibility of PT can be reached by co-digestion
12 with oil, without affecting antioxidant activity.

13

14 **Keywords:** *Calendula officinalis*, pentacyclic triterpenes, bioaccessibility, lipid digestion, excipient
15 foods

16

17 INTRODUCTION

18 *Calendula officinalis* L. (common name marigold) belongs to the order of Asterales and is a
19 member of the family Asteraceae. This herbaceous plant, native of the Mediterranean climate areas,
20 is traditionally cultivated in several countries for ornamental, medical and cosmetic purposes.
21 Although it is not extensively known, some edible uses have been described for flowers and leaves.
22 The fresh petals can be chopped and added to salads, curry or custard. The dried petals have a more
23 intense flavor and are used as seasoning in soups, cakes, drinks and baked products. A tea can be
24 prepared from the flowers and petals, and the leaves can be also eaten raw in salads.¹⁻³

25 The traditional medicinal use of the marigold is related to its great variety of phytochemicals of
26 bioactive interest, such as terpenoids, sterols, saponins, carotenoids and phenolic compounds,
27 mainly in flower extracts. Due to this complex composition, the extracts of marigold have been
28 related to activities such as antioxidant, antiinflammatory, immunostimulant, anticancer,
29 hepatoprotective, antimicrobial and wound healing.¹⁻⁴ The triterpenoids as pentacyclic triterpenes
30 (PT) have been described as one of the main responsible for the biological activities of marigold,
31 especially as anti-inflammatory.⁴ The typical PT of the marigold are monohydroxy alcohols (α -
32 amyirin, β -amyirin, taraxasterol and lupeol), and dihydroxyalcohols (faradiol, arnidiol, brein or
33 calenduladiol).

34 Taking into account the biological interest of all these compounds, the production of extracts of
35 marigold rich in these bioactive compounds is of current interest. Within the most popular methods
36 for production of plant extracts, the green technology of supercritical fluid extraction (SFE) is quite
37 popular nowadays, with special use in the extraction of compounds with low polarity that are
38 soluble in supercritical CO₂, such as the PT. The supercritical CO₂ extraction assisted by co-solvents
39 such as ethanol may also enhance the yield of extraction. In the specific case of marigold, diverse
40 studies have reported the use of SFE,⁵⁻⁷ but the use of co-solvents has been scarcely explored.⁷
41 Furthermore, many of them have been focused in the extraction and characterization of the essential
42 oil rich in sesquiterpenes,⁸⁻¹⁰ although the content in PT is not always reported.

43 It is important to remark that most of the described bioactive compounds of marigold are
44 compounds of a typical low polarity and high hydrophobicity, which leads to a limitation in their
45 potential use and bioactivity. However, it seems that the available information on the behavior of
46 PT during the gastrointestinal process, bioaccessibility and bioavailability is still scarce and
47 contradictory. It has been suggested that the bioavailability of PT is poor due to a difficult
48 solubilization in the aqueous media of the gastrointestinal tract, necessary for a proper absorption.¹¹
49 However, other studies reported that some PT of fruits and plants were effectively absorbed and
50 deposited in their intact forms in diverse tissues in mice.¹² In the specific case of the typical PT of
51 marigold, some studies have described that lupeol is bioavailable,¹³ whereas other studies have
52 suggested the opposite.^{14,15} Ching, Lin, Tan & Koh¹⁶ also described a low bioavailability of the
53 amyirin in mice, whereas diverse studies have shown that this compound is orally effective, which
54 would not be in agreement with a poor bioavailability.^{11,17} Concerning other PT from the marigold,
55 such as taraxasterol or faradiol, a lack of information on bioavailability has been found.

56 One of the factors that might be related to these inconclusive results could be the variability on the
57 composition of the digestion medium. In this respect, for most lipophilic compounds, it has been
58 demonstrated that their bioaccessibility can be improved by the coexistence of other lipids in the
59 intestinal tract.¹⁸ This is because the lipid digestion leads to the release of fatty acids and
60 monoglycerides that enhance the formation of micellar structures with bile salts and phospholipids.
61 These micelles will include other hydrophobic compounds present in the medium and in turn, the
62 dispersion and absorption of the compounds vehiculized by these micellar structures. In fact, this is
63 one of the fundamentals of current interest in the development of lipid-based delivery systems or
64 the recent term “excipient foods” (a food that increases the bioavailability of bioactive agents that
65 are co-ingested with it), for the improvement in the bioactivity of compounds for food and
66 nutraceuticals.^{19,20} On the other hand, the association of bioactive compounds with lipid
67 components has been suggested as a strategy with other advantages of interest, such as the
68 protection of labile compounds against the conditions of the gastrointestinal tract.^{21,22}

69 The aim of the present study was the production of a supercritical extract of *Calendula officinalis*,
70 in absence and presence of co-solvent, and the characterization on their terpene composition. The
71 subsequent *in vitro* gastrointestinal digestion of the extract was performed, both in absence and in
72 co-existence with olive oil, in order to evaluate the bioaccessibility and the distribution of particle
73 sizes of the digestion medium. Furthermore, the impact of the gastrointestinal digestion process on
74 the antioxidant activity of the extract was also evaluated.

75

76 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

77 **Reagents and Materials**

78 Dry *Calendula officinalis* flowers were purchased from a local herbalist supplier (Murcia, Spain).
79 The flowers were ground (particle size smaller than 500 μm) in a knife mill (Grindomix GM200
80 RETSCH). Extra virgin olive oil was purchased from a local supermarket.

81 Thymol, β -caryophyllene, valencene, cedrol, β -sitosterol, tocopherol and alkane mixture (C7-C30)
82 were from Sigma-Aldrich Chemie GmbH (Steinheim, Germany). The standard α -amyrin was from
83 Extrasynthese (Genay, France).

84 Trizma, maleic acid, Amano lipase A from *Aspergillus niger*, pepsin, pancreatin from porcine
85 pancreas, bile salts, phosphatidyl choline from egg yolk and 2,2-diphenyl-1-picryl-hydrazyl (DPPH)
86 were from Sigma-Aldrich Chemie GmbH (Steinheim, Germany).

87

88 **Supercritical extraction method**

89 Extractions were carried out in a pilot-scale supercritical fluid extractor (Thar Technology,
90 Pittsburgh, PA, USA, model SF2000) comprising a 2 L cylindrical extraction cell and two different
91 separators (S1 and S2), each of 0.5 L capacity, with control of temperature and pressure. The
92 extraction cell was loaded with 400 g of the milled marigold and the CO_2 flow rate was set to 70
93 g/min. The extractions were carried out using pure CO_2 or CO_2 with ethanol as cosolvent (10% p/p).
94 The extraction pressure and temperature were selected at 140 bar and 40 $^\circ\text{C}$ and were kept constant

95 for all experimental assays. The separator conditions were 40 bar and 40 °C. The total time
96 extraction was 180 min. Samples were stored at -20 °C until analysis.

97

98 **Analysis of terpene compounds of the extracts**

99 Samples were prepared at 15 mg/mL in chloroform:methanol (2:1, v/v) and were analyzed in an
100 Agilent 7890A system (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA) comprising a split/splitless
101 injector, an electronic pressure control, a G4513A auto-injector and a 5975C triple-axis mass
102 spectrometer detector. The column used was an Agilent HP-5MS capillary column (30 m × 0.25
103 mm i.d., 0.25 µm phase thickness). Helium was used as carrier gas at 2 mL/min. The injector
104 temperature was 260 °C and the mass spectrometer ion source and interface temperatures were 230
105 and 280 °C, respectively. The sample injections (1 µL) were performed in splitless mode. The
106 separation method of Crabas et al.⁸ was used with slight modifications. The oven temperature was
107 initially at 60 °C and increased to 250 °C at 4 °C/min, followed by an increase to 310 °C at 3
108 °C/min, and held for 5 min. The mass spectra were obtained by electronic impact at 70 eV. The
109 scan rate was 1.6 scan/s at a mass range of 30-700 amu. Identification of compounds was performed
110 by the NIST MS Data library, the retention indexes of the compounds, the mass spectra according
111 to literature, or according to those of pure commercial compounds whenever possible. Quantitation
112 of compounds was performed by calibration curves obtained from commercial standards whenever
113 possible: thymol was used for monoterpenes, caryophyllene and valencene were used for
114 hydrogenated sesquiterpenes, cedrol was used for oxygenated sesquiterpenes, sitosterol was used
115 for phytosterols, α-amyrin was used for PT, and tocopherol was quantitated by its own commercial
116 standard. Other compounds such as alkanes were also quantitated by their own commercial
117 compounds.

118

119 ***In vitro* gastrointestinal digestion**

120 The *in vitro* digestion model was based on Martin, Moran-Valero, Vázquez, Reglero & Torres²³
121 with brief modifications and the inclusion of a gastric phase. For gastric digestion, 30 mg of
122 marigold extract (ME) and 10 mg of lecithin were mixed with 14 mL of a gastric solution (150 mM
123 NaCl, 6 mM CaCl₂, pH 4.5). In case of the coexistence of dietary lipids, olive oil (OO) was added at
124 a ratio of ME to oil of 1:2 (w/w). The mixture was placed in an orbital incubator at 200 rpm and 37
125 °C. After 2 min of agitation to allow the dispersion of the components, the gastric digestion was
126 initiated by the addition of a fresh extract of gastric enzymes (170 mg of gastric lipase and 15 mg of
127 pepsin in 3 mL of gastric solution and stirred for 10 min). Reaction was continued during 45 min.
128 For intestinal digestion, a solution to simulate biliary secretion was prepared by mixing 0.1 g of
129 lecithin, 0.25 g of bile salts, 0.5 mL of 325 mM CaCl₂ solution, 1.5 mL of 3.25 mM NaCl solution,
130 and 10 mL of Trizma-maleate buffer 100 mM pH 7.5. This mixture was homogenized for 1 min at
131 3500 rpm (Ultra-Turrax IKA T18). Then, the biliary secretion was added to the gastric digestion
132 and shaken in the orbital incubator for 2 min at 200 rpm and 37 °C. The simulation of intestinal
133 digestion was started by the addition of fresh pancreatin extract (0.5 g of pancreatin in 3 mL of
134 Trizma-maleate buffer, stirred for 10 min and centrifuged at 1600 x g for 15 min). Reaction was
135 continued during 60 min. The *in vitro* digestion of each sample was performed at least in triplicate.

136

137 **Determination of bioaccessibility**

138 At the end of digestion the medium was submitted to centrifugation at 4000 rpm for 40 min (5810R
139 Eppendorf Iberica, Madrid, Spain). After centrifugation, an upper aqueous phase and a minor
140 precipitated phase were obtained. The aqueous phase was filtered in order to isolate the aqueous
141 solution containing the micellar structures (micellar phase, MP) from visible and non-solubilized
142 particles of the ME. The components of the ME included in the MP were extracted and analyzed by
143 GC-MS following the same procedure previously described.

144 The bioaccessibility of each compound was determined as the fraction of each compound that was
145 considered available for intestinal absorption, that is, included within the aqueous MP, as:

146 % bioaccessibility = (mg of compound in MP/mg of compound in digestion media) x 100

147

148 **Extraction of compounds from the digestion media**

149 At the end of digestion or after isolation of the MP, the components of the ME were extracted with
150 hexane:methyl tert-butyl ether (50:50, v/v) at a ratio of 3:1 (v/v) of solvent to sample. The mixture
151 was stirred for 1 min and centrifuged for 10 min at 4000 rpm (ScanSpeed mini, Micro Centrifuge).

152 A second extraction was performed with chloroform:methanol (2:1, v/v) at a ratio 3:1 (v/v) of
153 solvent to sample. The two organic phases obtained were mixed and the solvent was removed by
154 rotary evaporator. The obtained extract was solubilized in chloroform:methanol (2:1, v/v) at 15
155 mg/mL and analyzed by GC-MS following the same procedure previously described.

156

157 **Particle size distribution after *in vitro* digestion**

158 The particles size distribution of the isolated MP from the *in vitro* digestion of ME in absence and
159 presence of OO was measured. Furthermore, the particles size distribution was also determined for
160 two control samples: 1) the MP isolated after *in vitro* digestion in absence of ME and in absence of
161 OO, and 2) the MP isolated after *in vitro* digestion in absence of ME and in presence of OO. By this
162 procedure, it was possible to determine the particles size distribution of the digestion medium itself,
163 in order to distinguish the differences due to the presence of the experimental components.

164 The particle size distributions were analyzed by mean of laser diffraction technique. A Mastersizer
165 2000 instrument (Malvern Instruments Ltd., Malvern, Worcestershire, UK), equipped with a
166 dispersion unit of solid particles in liquids (Hydro 2000MU) working at 2000 rpm, was used.
167 Trizma-maleate buffer 100 mM pH 7.5 was used as dispersant. Assuming a volume distribution, the
168 largest particle size D₉₀ and the volume mean diameter D₄₃ were the reported parameters. Analyses
169 were performed in quintuplicate.

170

171 **Antioxidant activity of compounds by DPPH assay during *in vitro* digestion**

172 The antioxidant activity of the digestion media was measured before *in vitro* digestion and after
173 gastric and intestinal digestion by the DPPH test. The procedure of Martin, Moran-Valero, Casado,
174 Reglero & Torres²⁴ was used with brief modifications. The digestion medium was diluted in
175 methanol:chloroform (5:1 v/v) up to 0.8 mg of ME/mL. An aliquot (500 μ L) was added to 1500 μ L
176 of DPPH in methanol (0.06 mM). Samples were centrifuged at 12000 rpm for 5 min (miniSpin plus,
177 Eppendorf). Then, reaction was completed after 60 min at room temperature and darkness, and
178 absorbance was measured at 517 nm. Control experiments of the digestion medium in absence of
179 the tested compounds (ME and OO) were also performed following the same procedure. The
180 remaining DPPH concentration in the reaction medium was estimated by proper calibration curves
181 of DPPH.

182 Antioxidant activity was expressed as percentage of inhibition of DPPH as:

$$183 \quad \% \text{ inhibition DPPH} = 100 - [(\mu\text{g DPPH/mL}_{\text{sample}} / \mu\text{g DPPH/mL}_{\text{control}}) \times 100]$$

184

185 **Statistical analysis**

186 Statistical analyses were performed by means of the general linear model procedure of the SPSS
187 17.0 statistical package (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA) by one-way analysis of variance.
188 Differences were considered significant at $p \leq 0.05$. Post-hoc Tukey's tests were performed in order
189 to establish significant differences. Pearson's correlation tests were used to study the
190 bioaccessibility of compounds as related to their molecular properties.

191

192 **RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

193 **Characterization of supercritical extracts of *Calendula officinalis***

194 The presence or absence of co-solvent in the supercritical extraction of *Calendula officinalis* led to
195 some differences regarding yield and composition of the extract. The extraction yield of ME by CO₂
196 in absence of co-solvent was 2.1%, whereas that value was up to 7.5% in case of ethanol-CO₂
197 extraction. The identified compounds of both extracts are detailed in Table 1. More than 94% of the

198 volatile compounds were identified for both extracts. According to the area percentage, the major
199 abundance corresponded to alkanes (HC), followed by sesquiterpenes (S) and oxygenated
200 triterpenes (OT), in case of extraction without co-solvent. In case of ethanol-CO₂ extraction, a slight
201 qualitative difference was found, mainly due to a lower proportion of HC and a higher proportion of
202 OT. However, the major difference due to co-solvent was that the chromatographic areas for all the
203 compounds were lower than the CO₂ extraction without co-solvent (Table 1). Taking into account
204 the higher yield of the ethanol-CO₂ extraction, this result would suggest that the detected
205 compounds could be diluted with other extracted compounds but non-detected by GC-MS under the
206 used conditions.

207 In any case, the general composition of both ME was in agreement with previous similar studies
208 about supercritical extracts from this plant. Thus, α -cadinol, τ -cadinol, γ -cadinene and δ -cadinene
209 are typical volatile compounds described for marigold.^{8,10,25} Furthermore, in the current study, the
210 main detected PT were taraxasterol, lupeol, α -amyrin and β -amyrin, as well as diverse non-
211 identified sterols. The identification of PT from supercritical extracts of marigold has not been
212 usually described in most previous studies, but most of them were focused on the typical terpenes of
213 the essential oil of the extracts.

214 It is important to remark that the relative abundances of the compounds in Table 1 cannot be
215 considered to determine the major compounds of the extracts, due to their differences on
216 chromatographic responses. Therefore, taking into account the importance of characterizing the
217 extract due to its bioactive compounds of interest, especially PT, a proper quantitation as possible
218 was performed for some of the compounds with the available commercial standards. As shown in
219 Table 2, in absence of co-solvent, close to 15% of the chemical composition of the extract was
220 quantitated, being the OT the most abundant family of compounds. In the specific case of bioactive
221 PT (taraxasterol, lupeol, α -amyrin and β -amyrin), these compounds were close to 3% of the extract.
222 Furthermore, up to 5% of the extract was also quantitated as non-identified sterols.

223 Regarding the ethanol-CO₂ extract, due to the dilution effect with other extracted but non-identified
224 compounds, the total amount of quantitated compounds by GC-MS was lower than 5%, but
225 similarly to the CO₂ extract, the major compounds were the OT (4%) and the bioactive PT were
226 around 1.5% (Table 2).

227 As summary, both supercritical ME might be considered of interest due to their content on bioactive
228 PT, although the extraction of marigold in absence of co-solvent resulted in the preferred procedure.
229 Therefore, taking into account the interest of the bioactive PT, the following studies were performed
230 with the ME produced in absence of co-solvent.

231

232 **Bioaccessibility of supercritical extract of *Calendula officinalis***

233 After *in vitro* digestion of the ME, the bioaccessibility of the major quantitated compounds of the
234 extract was determined. Due to the complex composition of the extract, as well as the increased
235 complexity of the chromatographic analyses due to the co-elution of other compounds from the
236 digestion medium itself, a selection of compounds for the study of bioaccessibility was performed.
237 Such selection was based on the preferential characterization of the bioactive compounds of interest
238 (PT), as well as the consideration of other representative compounds of each chemical family of the
239 extract (SH, OS and HC) that were present in the extract at concentration $\geq 0.1\%$ at least. The
240 selected compounds and their values of bioaccessibility are shown in Table 3.

241 According to Table 3, the bioaccessible fraction of the compounds was quite variable, since
242 percentages higher than 80% were found for some compounds, whereas other compounds showed
243 values lower than 50%. In general, it seemed that the bioaccessibility of the family of compounds
244 decreased in the following order: SH (84%) > OS (81%) > OT (77%) > HC (42%). Thus, it could be
245 considered that most terpenes, included the PT, showed a high bioaccessibility, since more than
246 75% of the amount of terpenes were found within the bioaccessible MP, including the bioactive PT
247 (Table 3). The available information about the bioaccessibility of terpenes in general is scarce, and
248 bioaccessibility values of PT in particular has not been found in the scientific literature, whereas

249 contradictory results have been reported about the bioavailability of compounds such as lupeol or
250 amyriins.^{11, 13-17} According to the obtained results, the present study showed that the studied PT of a
251 supercritical extract of ME might have high bioaccessibility.

252 Diverse reasons might be considered to explain the observed results. In general, the bioaccessibility
253 of compounds in the aqueous medium of the intestinal lumen is determined by their solubility.^{26,27}

254 This solubility is not a problem for those compounds with a good hydrosolubility or
255 hydrophilic/lipophilic balance that ensure its dispersion in the medium, either directly, or indirectly,
256 by inclusion in vesicles, emulsion droplets, lamellar or micellar structures of bile salts and
257 phospholipids naturally present in the intestinal tract. In fact, absorption of lipophilic products
258 takes place supported by these structures of the MP, which enhances the transport of such products
259 to enterocytes through the unstirred water layer close to the microvillous membrane, where they are
260 absorbed.^{26,27} According to this theory, most of terpenes might show a proper dispersion in the
261 aqueous media after *in vitro* digestion. On the contrary, alkanes might not be so effectively
262 dispersed within the medium and hence their lower bioaccessibility.

263 In order to understand whether the obtained results were related to the lipophilicity of the
264 compounds, the logP value of each individual substance listed in Figure 1 was considered (Food
265 Database FooDB, www.foodb.ca). As it is illustrated in Figure 1, a negative correlation was found
266 between the logP value of the compounds and their bioaccessibility ($r = -0.771$, $P < 0.001$).
267 Therefore, the higher lipophilicity of the compounds, the worse the bioaccessibility is. Thus, logP
268 values lower than 8 might be preferred for a high bioaccessibility (closer to 80%). All PT identified
269 in ME showed logP values around 6.

270 Another molecular property that has been popularly related to the bioavailability of drugs is the
271 molecular flexibility, due to the number of rotatable bonds (NRB) described by Veber, Johnson,
272 Cheng, Smith, Ward & Kopple²⁸. A low NRB value has been suggested as one strong criterion for
273 drug candidates with proper bioavailability, although the exact reason for such relation has not been
274 established. According to Figure 2, a strong negative correlation was found between the NRB value

275 of the studied compounds (Molinspiration Cheminformatics, Bratislava, Slovak Republic) and their
276 bioaccessibility ($r = -0.860$, $P < 0.001$). Therefore, the higher the molecular flexibility, the worse
277 the bioaccessibility is. Thus, NRB values of 0 or 1 might be desirable for a high bioaccessibility of
278 the studied compounds. This was considered an interesting result, since previous information on the
279 relation between the molecular flexibility and bioaccessibility of compounds has not been
280 described, but only the relation of NRB with bioavailability.

281 Therefore, according to the obtained results, the compounds of bioactive interest of the ME showed
282 high bioaccessibilities that might be related to their favorable molecular properties. At any case,
283 further studies at this respect would be necessary in order to understand whether such proper
284 bioaccessibility might lead to a positive bioavailability and bioactivity.

285

286 **Bioaccessibility of *Calendula officinalis* supercritical extract co-digested with olive oil**

287 Despite that the studied compounds showed a proper bioaccessibility, it was considered interesting
288 the study of the role of the coexistence of lipids (olive oil, OO) during the digestion process in order
289 to evaluate whether it would be possible to reach a complete bioaccessibility of the bioactive
290 compounds of interest. Preliminary studies were performed in order to find the best ratio ME to oil
291 that allowed the best bioaccessibility for most compounds (data not shown). This ratio was
292 established as 1:2 (w/w) and the corresponding results are shown in Figure 3. In general, a higher
293 bioaccessibility due to the OO factor was found ($P < 0.001$). The different chemical families
294 increased around 20% their bioaccessibility, and most compounds of interest reached values of
295 bioaccessibility closer to 100%.

296 During lipid digestion, the major hydrolysis products as fatty acids and monoglycerides are
297 released. These compounds lead to the formation of micellar structures with bile salts and
298 phospholipids, which is necessary for the proper absorption of fats by enterocytes.²⁷ This increase
299 in the micellar surface compared to the absence of oil increases the available structures for inclusion
300 of other hydrophobic compounds present in the aqueous media and hence, their bioaccessibility is

301 enhanced.¹⁸⁻²⁰ This mechanism would be related to the results obtained in the present study.
302 Therefore, the current study showed that despite the bioaccessibility of bioactive compounds such
303 as PT from a supercritical extract of marigold was high; the co-digestion with particularly low
304 levels of a typical dietary fat would be enough to reach a complete bioaccessibility of such
305 compounds. In this respect, according to the term of “excipient food” recently described by
306 McClements et al.,¹⁹ as a food that increases the bioavailability of bioactive agents that are co-
307 ingested with it, olive oil might be a potential candidate as “excipient food” to enhance the
308 bioaccessibility of compounds of ME in general, and of bioactive PT in particular. As far as we
309 know, previous studies about the effect of coexistence of oils on the gastrointestinal digestion
310 behavior and bioaccessibility of PT have not been described in the scientific literature.

311

312 **Particle size distribution after *in vitro* digestion**

313 The particle size distribution of the isolated MP was characterized in order to deepen the
314 understanding of the hypothesis that a better bioaccessibility of the compounds was due to an
315 enhanced dispersion by digested lipids. Previously, we considered necessary to understand the
316 typical particles size distribution of the own MP in absence of any of the experimental compounds,
317 that is, in absence of ME and OO. As shown in Figure 4.a, there were two major peaks, one in the
318 range of 0.2 μm , and a second one in the range of 1 μm . Furthermore, another abundant volume of
319 particles was found within a wide range of sizes between 4 and 240 μm . This distribution led to a
320 MP characterized by particles most of them lower than 25 μm (D_{90}) and a volume mean diameter
321 around 11 μm (D_{43}). It is complicated to determine the precise components of the medium
322 responsible of such distribution, but it might probably be related to the particles formed by
323 phospholipids, bile salts, either individually or in combination as micelles or vesicles.²⁹

324 When OO was digested, the particle size distribution of the MP changed (Figure 4.b). The typical
325 modes at 0.2 and 1 μm were also present, but the area of the mode at 0.2 μm was higher, whereas
326 the modes at 1 and 4-240 μm were much lower. Thus, the MP was characterized by particles most

327 of them lower than 2 μm (D_{90}) and a volume mean diameter around 7 μm (D_{43}). The obtained
328 results would suggest that the hydrolysis products of OO, mainly fatty acids and monoglycerides,
329 contributed to an increase in the number of particles of lower size within the MP. These observed
330 results were quite useful since they could confirm that the *in vitro* digestion model led to a
331 physiological and favorable situation to enhance the dispersion of other lipophilic compounds in the
332 aqueous media.

333 When the ME was digested in absence of OO, the typical modes of the medium at 0.2 and 1 μm
334 were present again; however, a relevant decrease was produced at the expense of an increase in the
335 abundance of bigger particles (Figure 4.c). In fact, three new modes of particles appeared in the
336 range of 6 μm , 65 μm and 500 μm . Thus, in presence of ME, the MP was characterized by bigger
337 particles, because the 10% of particles were even higher than 190 μm (D_{90}) and the volume mean
338 diameter was around 47 μm (D_{43}). This distribution was quite different compared to the control
339 samples (Figure 4.a and 4.b). Therefore, it could be thought that the obtained results might be
340 mainly related to particles of the ME dispersed in the aqueous media, either in isolation or by
341 interacting with components of the medium.

342 When the ME was digested in co-existence with OO, the basic modes of the medium at 0.2 and 1
343 μm increased again and the big particle sizes previously observed for the ME sample decreased at
344 the expense of the formation of a wide mode in the range of 15-200 μm (Figure 4.d). Thus, in
345 presence of OO, the MP from the digestion of ME was characterized by lower particles than in
346 absence of OO, being most of them lower than 28 μm (D_{90}) and a volume mean diameter around 9
347 μm (D_{43}). Those values were closer to those obtained for the control sample of MP in absence of
348 ME and OO (Figure 4.a). This might confirm our proposed theory that hydrolysis products of lipids
349 could enhance the dispersion of hydrophobic compounds of ME, by increasing the number of lower
350 size particles.

351 Therefore, the study of the distribution of particle sizes after *in vitro* digestion of ME showed that
352 the co-digestion of the extract with low levels of a typical dietary fat might enhance the dispersion

353 of the marigold components within the aqueous phase of the intestinal medium and, in turn, would
354 enhance its bioaccessibility (Table 3). As far to our knowledge, previous studies on the particle size
355 distribution of the aqueous medium after digestion of ME, either with or without oils, have not been
356 described in the scientific literature. In any case, further studies would be necessary in order to
357 confirm the observed evidences, taking into account that the diluting and stirring conditions
358 commonly used for particle size measurement might lead to the formation of artefacts.

359

360 **Antioxidant activity of *Calendula officinalis* supercritical extract during *in vitro* digestion**

361 The modification of the antioxidant activity of diverse compounds, either negatively or positively,
362 after the process and conditions of gastrointestinal digestion has been previously described. In case
363 of a detrimental effect after digestion, the association of bioactive compounds with lipid
364 components has been reported as a strategy to protect those labile compounds from the conditions
365 of the gastrointestinal tract.^{21,22} Therefore, taking into account that some components of marigold
366 have been described as antioxidants, it was considered interesting the study of the impact of the
367 digestion process on such activity, either in absence or in presence of olive oil.

368 As shown in Figure 5, the ability of the ME to inhibit the DPPH radical significantly increased with
369 the course of the gastrointestinal digestion ($P=0.006$). Such increase was especially significant after
370 intestinal digestion for both treatments. Furthermore, the final inhibitory activity that was observed
371 after intestinal digestion was quite similar between treatments, regardless of the presence or absence
372 of OO. Thus, the inhibitory activity of ME increased after gastrointestinal digestion around 50%
373 and 40% for the treatments in absence and presence of OO, respectively. The improvement of the
374 antioxidant activity of compounds during the gastrointestinal process has been previously described,
375 especially for polyphenols, due to their release during the hydrolysis processes from other complex
376 molecules.³⁰ As far as we know, previous information about the antioxidant activity of compounds
377 from ME as affected by gastrointestinal digestion has not been described.

378 Therefore, the observed results showed that the antioxidant effect of ME was not negatively
379 affected, but rather enhanced by the *in vitro* gastrointestinal process. Additionally, it seemed that
380 the better dispersion of the extract that was found in presence of OO was not related to these results,
381 at least in the case of intestinal digestion, since during gastric digestion the antioxidant activity was
382 significantly higher in presence of OO. Other *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies would be necessary in
383 order to evaluate whether these preliminary results would be related to enhanced antioxidant
384 activities of a digested ME.

385 As a summary, the present study showed that supercritical extraction in absence of co-solvent is the
386 preferred procedure for producing a marigold extract rich in bioactive compounds such as
387 pentacyclic triterpenes. Although that such bioactive compounds show a good bioaccessibility, it
388 can be even improved by the co-digestion with particularly low levels of a typical dietary fat such
389 as olive oil, thanks to a better dispersion of the extract in the aqueous media during gastrointestinal
390 digestion. Additionally, the gastrointestinal process enhances the antioxidant activity of the extract,
391 regardless of the co-digestion with olive oil. The obtained results are of interest either to obtaining a
392 deeper knowledge on the potential of the marigold plant as a possible bioactive ingredient of foods,
393 as well as to contributing to the general knowledge on the gastrointestinal digestion of bioactive
394 compounds such as pentacyclic triterpenes, together with other typical compounds of supercritical
395 extracts of plants in general, such as sesquiterpenes or alkanes.

396

397 **ABBREVIATIONS USED**

ME	Marigold extract
PT	Pentacyclic triterpenes
OO	Olive oil
SFE	Supercritical fluid extraction
MP	Micellar phase
HC	Alkanes

S	Sesquiterpenes
SH	Sesquiterpenes hydrocarbons
OT	Oxygenated triterpenes
OS	Oxygenated sesquiterpenes
NRB	Number of rotatable bonds

398

399 **ACKNOWLEDGMENTS**

400 Joaquín Navarro del Hierro thanks the Universidad Autónoma de Madrid for funding his
401 collaboration scholarship during his Official Master's Degree studies.

402

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488

489 **Funding**

490 This work was supported by the Ministerio de Economía y Competitividad, Spain (AGL2013-
491 48943-C2-1-R) and the Community of Madrid, Spain (ALIBIRD-CM S2013/ABI-2728).

492

493 **Notes**

494 The authors declare no competing financial interest.

495

496 **Figure Captions**

497

498 **Figure 1.** Correlation between lipophilicity (logP) of compounds from supercritical marigold
499 extract and their bioaccessibility (%)

500

501 **Figure 2.** Correlation between molecular flexibility (NRB) of compounds from supercritical
502 marigold extract and their bioaccessibility (%)

503

504 **Figure 3.** Bioaccessibility (%) of compounds from supercritical marigold extract as affected by
505 olive oil during *in vitro* digestion. Bars within the same compound are significantly different if $p \leq$
506 0.05 (*), $p \leq 0.01$ (**) or $p \leq 0.001$ (***).

507

508 **Figure 4.** Volume particle size distribution of the digestion media after *in vitro* digestion. Isolated
509 aqueous micellar phase after *in vitro* digestion of a) without marigold and without olive oil, b)
510 without marigold and with olive oil, c) with marigold and without olive oil, and d) with marigold
511 and with olive oil.

512

513 **Figure 5.** Evolution of the antioxidant activity of supercritical marigold extract throughout *in vitro*
514 digestion. Different letters within the same treatment are significantly different. Bars within the same color
515 are significantly higher if $p \leq 0.05$ (*) or $p \leq 0.001$ (***).

516

517

518

519

Table 1. GC-MS Characterization of Supercritical Extracts of *Calendula Officinalis*

RI	Compound	CO ₂		Ethanol-CO ₂	
		Area	%	Area	%
1295	Thymol	1535567	0.74	414731	0.91
1304	Carvacrol	613051	0.30	185772	0.41
1351	α -Cubebene	416655	0.20	105666	0.23
1378	α -Copaene	968862	0.47	272124	0.60
1391	β -Cubebene	625195	0.30	113123	0.25
1430	β -Gurjunene	481604	0.23	69838	0.15
1442	β -Humulene	95765	0.05	96099	0.21
1464	Alloaromadendrene	898623	0.43	163108	0.36
1478	γ -Muurolene	901727	0.43	248135	0.55
1487	β -Ionone	617759	0.30	119421	0.26
1490	β -Selinene	363937	0.18	33297	0.07
1497	(+)-Ledene	2385902	1.15	495858	1.09
1502	α -Muurolene	1756737	0.85	464359	1.02
1516	γ -Cadinene	5778816	2.78	2006429	4.42
1525	δ -Cadinene	6024229	2.90	1726232	3.80
1528	Dihydroactinidiolide	2694113	1.30	795656	1.75
1535	Cadina-1(2),4-diene	1330919	0.64	115862	0.25
1539	α -Cadinene	1086998	0.52	249607	0.55
1544	α -Calacorene	408864	0.20	61864	0.14
1593	Viridiflorol	3118592	1.50	389411	0.86
1610	1-10-di-epi-cubenol	805223	0.39	212891	0.47
1616	δ -Cadinol	749509	0.36	151504	0.33
1629	Cubenol	824483	0.40	190310	0.42
1645	τ -Cadinol	10030609	4.83	2369705	5.22
1648	n.i. oxygenated sesquiterpene	1062037	0.51	264170	0.58
1652	β -Eudesmol	2101899	1.01	430441	0.95
1658	α -Cadinol	12114169	5.83	2456127	5.41
1670	n.i. ^a	1095520	0.53	218458	0.48
1711	3-Hydroxy-5,6-epoxy- β -ionone	1793930	0.86	n.d. ^b	n.d.
1740	1-cyclohexanone, 2-methyl-2-(3-methyl-2-oxobutyl)	10426982	5.02	2808684	6.18
1779	9,10-	16481274	7.93	5541526	12.20

dimethyltricyclo[4.2.1.1.(2,5)]decane-
9,10-diol

1840	n.i.	857747	0.41	n.d.	n.d.
1846	Hexahydrofarnesyl acetone	4377593	2.11	n.d.	n.d.
1901	Nonadecane	4110435	1.98	862927	1.90
1970	Verticiol	2312239	1.11	547645	1.21
1996	Palmitic acid, ethyl ester	315697	0.15	111172	0.24
2001	Eicosane	980904	0.47	163966	0.36
2101	Heneicosane	6802339	3.27	1116421	2.46
2201	Docosane	630054	0.30	104863	0.23
2302	Tricosane	8930569	4.30	1385382	3.05
2402	Tetracosane	1111476	0.54	148787	0.33
2503	Pentacosane	13651831	6.57	1894387	4.17
2601	Hexacosane	980678	0.47	89782	0.20
2708	Heptacosane	18232039	8.78	1943518	4.28
2797	Octacosane	2050351	0.99	242332	0.53
2892	Nonacosane	19427953	9.35	2277964	5.01
2978	Triacontane	2191196	1.05	n.d.	n.d.
-	Hentriacontane	11165954	5.38	1739227	3.83
-	α -Tocopherol	827910	0.40	442105	0.97
-	Dotriacontane	180722	0.09	n.d.	n.d.
-	n.i. sterol	175177	0.08	n.d.	n.d.
-	n.i. sterol	728069	0.35	540417	1.19
-	n.i. sterol	2017797	0.97	710705	1.56
-	β -Amyrenone	578061	0.28	262928	0.58
-	β -Amyrin	2940308	1.42	1433928	3.16
-	n.i. sterol	595111	0.29	287959	0.63
-	α -Amyrin + Lupeol	4327976	2.08	2095993	4.61
-	n.i. oxygenated triterpene	643359	0.31	226066	0.50
-	Taraxasterol	6422306	3.09	3910398	8.61
-	n.i.	565285	0.27	128466	0.28
	Oxygenated monoterpenes		2.3		3.1
	Sesquiterpenes hydrocarbons		11.6		14.0
	Oxygenated sesquiterpenes		14.3		13.7

Oxygenated diterpenes	1.1	1.2
Oxygenated triterpenes	7.3	17.9
Alkanes	43.5	26.3
Other compounds	16.1	18.6
Total identified compounds	96.3	94.8

^a n.i. = non identified; ^b n.d. = non detected

Table 2. Quantitative Composition (mg/g) of Supercritical Extract of *Calendula Officinalis*

Compound	CO ₂	Ethanol-CO ₂
Thymol	0.60	0.16
Carvacrol	0.24	0.07
α -Cubebene	0.18	0.05
α -Copaene	0.42	0.12
β -Cubebene	0.27	0.05
β -Gurjunene	0.21	0.03
β -Humulene	0.04	0.04
Alloaromadendrene	0.39	0.07
γ -Muurolene	0.39	0.11
β -Selinene	0.18	0.02
(+)-Ledene	1.19	0.25
α -Muurolene	0.88	0.23
γ -Cadinene	2.89	1.00
δ -Cadinene	3.02	0.86
Cadina-1(2),4-diene	0.67	0.06
α -Cadinene	0.54	0.13
α -Calacorene	0.20	0.03
Viridiflorol	1.11	0.14
1-10-di-epi-cubenol	0.29	0.08
δ -Cadinol	0.27	0.05
Cubenol	0.29	0.07
τ -Cadinol	3.56	0.84
n.i. ^a Oxygenated sesquiterpene	0.38	0.09
β -Eudesmol	0.75	0.15
α -Cadinol	4.30	0.87
Nonadecane	1.02	0.21
Eicosane	0.25	0.04
Heneicosane	1.81	0.30
Docosane	0.18	0.03
Tricosane	2.62	0.41
Tetracosane	0.34	0.05

Pentacosane	4.64	0.64
Hexacosane	0.38	0.03
Heptacosane	8.55	0.91
Octacosane	1.19	0.14
Nonacosane	14.27	1.67
Triacotane	2.13	n.d. ^b
Hentriacotane	10.83	1.69
α -Tocopherol	1.29	0.69
Dotriacotane	0.18	n.d.
n.i. sterol	2.65	n.d.
n.i. sterol	11.00	8.16
n.i. sterol	30.48	10.74
β -Amyrenone	1.20	0.54
β -Amyrin	6.08	2.97
n.i. sterol	8.99	4.35
α -Amyrin + Lupeol	8.96	4.34
n.i. oxygenated triterpene	1.33	0.47
Taraxasterol	13.29	8.09
Oxygenated monoterpenes	0.8	0.2
Sesquiterpenes hydrocarbons	11.5	3.1
Oxygenated sesquiterpenes	10.9	2.3
Oxygenated triterpenes	85.5	40.4
Alkanes	48.6	6.1
Total quantitated compounds	156.9	52.1

^a n.i. = non identified; ^b n.d. = non detected

Table 3. Bioaccessibility (%) of Supercritical Extract of *Calendula Officinalis*

Compound	Chemical group ^a	Bioaccessibility
γ-Cadinene	SH	79.3 ± 9.7
δ-Cadinene	SH	87.9 ± 11.8
τ-Cadinol	OS	75.1 ± 3.4
α-Cadinol	OS	87.1 ± 3.7
Nonadecane	HC	48.1 ± 2.0
Tricosane	HC	57.2 ± 11.0
Pentacosane	HC	48.3 ± 2.8
Heptacosane	HC	13.8 ± 2.4
α-Tocopherol	OT	71.1 ± 6.5
β-Amyrin	OT	79.8 ± 4.8
α-Amyrin + Lupeol	OT	82.1 ± 8.8
Taraxasterol	OT	75.5 ± 2.1
Sesquiterpenes hydrocarbons		83.6 ± 10.8
Oxygenated sesquiterpenes		81.1 ± 3.6
Oxygenated triterpenes		77.1 ± 2.9
Alkanes		41.8 ± 3.5

^a SH = sesquiterpene hydrocarbon, OS = oxygenated sesquiterpene, HC = alkanes, OT = oxygenated triterpene

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

Bars within the same compound are significantly different if $p \leq 0.05$ (*), $p \leq 0.01$ (**) or $p \leq 0.001$ (***).

Figure 4.

Isolated aqueous micellar phase after *in vitro* digestion of a) without marigold and without olive oil, b) without marigold and with olive oil, c) with marigold and without olive oil, and d) with marigold and with olive oil

Figure 5.

Different letters within the same treatment are significantly different. Bars within the same color are significantly higher if $p \leq 0.05$ (*) or $p \leq 0.001$ (***)

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